
Effects of Problem-Based Instructional Strategy on Students' Academic Performance in Financial Accounting in Technical Colleges in Delta State

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated how a problem-based teaching approach impacts the academic achievement of financial accounting students in technical colleges located in Delta State. The aim of the study was to assess the academic performance of students who were taught using traditional methods compared to those who experienced the problem-based teaching approach in financial accounting. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses. It utilized a quasi-experimental design featuring a pretest and posttest with a non-randomized control group. The population for the study comprised all 92 vocational II students enrolled in Delta State technical colleges. The sample included 54 financial accounting students. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select the participants. The instrument used for data collection was the Financial Accounting Achievement Test (FAAT), which was validated by three experts and showed a reliability coefficient of 0.89; was achieved using the Kuder-Richardson formula 21. Data related to the research questions were analyzed using mean and standard deviation, while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to evaluate the null hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. The findings indicated that students who were taught financial accounting with a problem-based teaching strategy achieved higher scores compared to those who received instruction through traditional teaching methods. Additionally, there was a notable difference in performance between male and female students who were taught financial accounting using the problem-based teaching strategy. It was concluded that effective teaching of the subject is crucial for successful accounting education by employing effective instructional techniques. Nonetheless, the research suggested, among other things, that financial accounting courses in technical colleges ought to be delivered through a problem-based teaching approach, regardless of the students' gender. The Ministry of Technical Education and the Post Primary Education Board should arrange workshops, seminars, and symposiums for financial accounting instructors on the significance of utilizing.

KEYWORDS: Students, academic performance, problem-based teaching strategy.

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INTRODUCTION

One of the transformative tools of any society is education. It is a well-structured instructional designed used to communicate knowledge, skills and understanding. The major aim of education is to make the individual to be socially, mentally, emotionally and morally sound so as to be able to contribute his quarter to the development of his society. The achievement of the stated aim of education will depend on students' academic performance in external examinations. According to Aworanti (2013) one wonders if the goals of vocational and technical education can be achieved considering the rate of students' poor performance in external examinations in technical colleges

Technical and vocational colleges are specialized institutions set up to develop the skills and knowledge in secondary school students. The institution offers both practical and theoretical subjects like mathematics, English language, basic electricity, building, auto, fabrication, carpentry/woodwork, catering, and business trade (financial accounting, commerce, word processing etc.), with well-equipped laboratories for effective teaching and learning. The aim of this vibrant education is to equip students with vocational and technical skills (FRN, 2004). Technical college was established to reduce the rate of unemployment among Nigerian youths and to produce skilled manpower that will work in various sectors of the economy (Emefiele, 2023). It is expected that the graduates of technical colleges are equipped with knowledge and skills that would make them to be employable or to be self-employed after their final examination.

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Examination bodies like National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) and West African Examination Council (WAEC), are charged with the responsibilities of assessing students' competencies in their final examination, after which they would be awarded, National Technical Certificate (NTC)/National Business Certificate (NBC) and West African School Certificate (WASSC) respectively. The National Board for Technical Education was set up by the federal government of Nigeria in 1977, with the sole responsibility to supervise, accredit, and regulate the affairs of technical institutions in Nigeria. In Delta State, technical colleges are co-managed by the Ministry of Education, Ministry of Technical Education, and Post-primary Education Board (Emefiele, 2023). The ministry of technical education monitor the subjects offered in technical colleges on routine basis.

Financial accounting is one of the subjects offered in technical colleges in vocational classes in Delta State. It is also among the subjects taken in National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) and West African Examination Council (WAEC). This subject is meant to equip the recipients with the competency needed to keep basic accounting records. It involves the collection, recording, summarizing, analyzing and reporting in monetary terms information about a business organization to the users of such information (Owenbuigie and Iyoha, 2017). According to Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidili (2016), the knowledge of financial accounting is necessary for every individual and business endeavour.

Financial accounting is concerned with the documentation of income and expenses, which are essential for any serious business operation. The primary goals of accounting include offering specialized training designed to prepare students for careers in various accounting sectors; providing foundational knowledge that equips students to fulfill their responsibilities as consumers, employees, and members of society; giving background education that aids students in getting ready for other professional paths that may require advanced studies in bookkeeping and accounting; and developing accounting skills for personal use and future endeavors.

The Objectives of accounting according to Osuala (2004) are to:

- (a) Learn how to keep better records for personal and home use;
- (b) Study financial accounting records and reports as an integral part to the functioning of any business enterprise;
- (c) Understand the concept of assets, liabilities and proprietorship so that the fluctuation in business and records may be correctly interpreted; and
- (d) Interpret and analyses business and records in terms of customers.

Despite the importance of accounting in daily activities of individuals, businesses and government, the persistent poor performance of technical college students in the subject has not been adequately addressed. Records available showed that there has been a decline in the academic performance level of technical college students in financial accounting (Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidili, 2016). In order to meet the goals of accounting education, it is essential to employ effective instructional strategy that foster meaningful teaching and learning. Research has identified numerous factors contributing to students' low performance in financial accounting, leading to various efforts aimed at addressing this issue. The ineffective teaching methods and strategies previously utilized are mainly to blame for students' underachievement in the subject (Okon, 2002).

It is apparent therefore, that the traditional methods/strategies employed by majority of accounting teachers in most schools in Nigeria are largely the caused of students' low performance. The students' dismal performance in financial accounting is noticeable in the entire students' results in examinations like the General Certification in Education (GCE), National Business and Technical Examination Board (NABTEB) and Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (SSCE). The conventional instructional methods of teaching financial accounting like the use of discussion, demonstration, Socratic/questioning, project methods just to mention but few have been adopted but appeared not to have yielded the intended outcome neither have they impact the students with the requisite knowledge and skills wholistically.

Okon (2002) equally believes that these traditional methods/strategies are not challenging enough to the needs of the students.

Bearing in mind that financial accounting is a quantitative subject; It is of paramount important to investigate the significance impact of problem-based instructional strategy on the academic achievement in financial accounting of male and female students offering the subject. In order realize these laudable objectives as it is stated, accounting teachers ought to employ productive or effective instructional strategy to ensure the teaching and learning of accounting is a meaningful endeavor. It is on record that, a good number of students enroll this subject "accounting" in secondary schools but sadly they perform dismally in external examinations regardless of their gender. Thus, the issue of low academic performance of students in financial accounting, particular in technical colleges in Delta State has been a source of concern to all well-meaning citizens. It is a trite fact that, the quality of education whether good or bad rest with the teachers as mirrored in the performance of the students. The students' academic performance in internal and external examination, over time, had been used to explain excellence of teachers within the teaching careers and professions.

Teachers have been shown to have an important influence on student academic achievement and they also play crucial roles in educational attainment because the teacher is ultimately responsible for translating policy into action and principles based on

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practice during interaction with the students (Afe, 2001). Both teaching and learning depends on teachers; no wonder an effective teacher has been conceptualized as one who produces desired results in the course of his duty as a teacher (Uchefuna, 2001).

Bearing in mind, the government's prodigious investment in education, its outcome on the basis of quality of students or performance have been observed to be unmatched with government spending. Based on the noticeable deterioration in the academic performance, attitude and the increasingly decline in the general values of public secondary school students, one wonders if the obvious failure rates and poor quality among the students are not the result of the instructional approach adopted. In other words, the ineffectiveness of accounting teachers or poor classroom interaction with the students are likely to be responsible for the observed very low academic performance of students in financial accounting in schools and technical colleges in Delta State.

This is the reason Ndinechi and Obidile (2013), opines that lecture method is teacher-centered method and has been found to make students passive learners and should not be solely used in the teaching of financial accounting. Azih and Nwosu (2011) indicated that student-centred methods which are characterized by active involvement of students in the teaching and learning process could be the important factor for improving students' performance in financial accounting.

Modes of instructional delivery or methods of teaching are often based on some theories of teaching and learning. The theory of constructivism is one among some of these notable theories of teaching in recent times. The constructivists hold the view that learning should primarily involve the learner and that it facilitates the learners' ability to conceptualize learning contents (Nwanze, 2016). The rationale evolved from the inclination that knowledge is a humanly constructed and that this knowledge is constructed are in cultural and social dimensions. Thus, meaningful learning takes place when the learners are socially involved (Vygotsky, 1978). Problem-based instructional strategy is among these strategies. These strategies are student-centred methods in nature and they include problem-based strategy, guided discovery and inquiry methods and numerous others.

Problem-based learning as a strategy for learning consists of carefully selected and designed problems that demand from the learner acquisition of critical knowledge, problem solving proficiency, self-directed learning strategies and team participation skills (Maloney, 2004).

It minimizes the teacher's responsibilities during classroom instructions/interactions and pushes the learning responsibilities or tasks to the learners; where learners are active participants rather than being a mere passive learner in the classroom activities as opposed to the lecture method. Problem-based teaching/learning is an example of constructivist learning strategy which poses significant contextualized real-world situations and provides guidance, resources and instruction to learning as they develop content knowledge and problem-solving skills (Yager, 1991).

The first task for the teacher in problem-based teaching is to guide the student to identify the problems and help them to link with previous knowledge (Anyafulude, 2014). The student in a small group solves the problem cooperatively among themselves in a small group, explain what they know, develop initial plans and organize their knowledge, attempt to solve the problems with several modifications, derive learning goals and organize further work (Afolabi&Akinbobola, 2012). Finally, the results are presented to larger groups through the guidance of the teacher and the students are allowed to reflect on the learning that has taken place (Afolabi&Akinbobola, 2012).

Research-based evidence has shown that problem-based teaching strategy improves students' learning outcome (Anyafulude, 2014; Eze, Ezenwafor&Obidile, 2016). Anyafulude (2014) found that problem-based teaching strategy have positive effect on students' academic achievement. Anyafulude concluded that students/learners exposed to problem-based teaching strategy outperformed students exposed to the lecture method of traditional method of teaching.

Celik, Onder and Silay (2011) reaffirmed the superiority of problem-based teaching strategy over the lecture method in improving students' academic achievement. According to Eze, Ezenwafor and Obidile (2016), problem-based instructional strategy has the tendency of enhancing students' academic performance in financial accounting. The direction of this study therefore, is to investigate the likely effects of Problem-based instructional strategy on student's academic performance/achievements in financial accounting.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The observed persistent disappointing performance of technical college students in financial accounting has not been given the solution it deserves. The sad performance of students is likely the result of the ineffective instructional method of teaching employed by most financial accounting teachers. Over the years, several instructional methods and approaches have been employed. These comprised methods like lecture, demonstration, discussion and project. These methods however, could not impact the students neither were they able to improve on the achievement of students in financial accounting in both internal and external examinations. The increasing decline in the academic achievements of technical college students in financial accounting are obvious from the available records. It is important to note that, the teaching of accounting depends heavily on the effective teaching method of the subject and a good blend of other available instructional resources. One method of teaching that appears not been used regularly in financial accounting is the problem-based instructional strategy. What is however not too clear to the

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researcher, is the extent to which problem-based teaching strategy would impact on the students offering of financial accounting in technical colleges in Delta State, hence, the study.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The major focus of this research therefore, was to find out the impact of Problem-based instructional strategy on student's academic performance in financial accounting. The study specifically determined the mean academic performance of:

1. Students taught using conventional methods and students taught with Problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting;
2. Students taught using Problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting based on gender.

Research Questions

The following research questions directed the study

1. What is the academic performance of students taught using conventional methods and student taught employing problem-based instructional strategy?
2. What is the academic performance of students taught using problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting based on gender?

Null Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students taught using conventional methods and students taught using problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting
2. There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students taught using problem-based instructional strategy based on gender.

METHODS

Quasi-experimental design was employed for the study. The non-equivalent control group, pretest, post-test design was specifically used for the study. Since the students that were involved in the study had already been organized into intact classes, the quasi-experimental design was adopted. According to Nworgu (2006) quasi experimental studies does not allow for randomization of subjects to experimental and control groups. In support of this design, Borg and Gall (2007) stated that it is a suitable alternative to experimental design when randomization is not used or applied. Below explains the design that was used:

Group	Pre-test	Treatment	Post-test
Problem-based Teaching Method (experimental)	Q ₁ X ₁ Q ₂		
Conventional/Lecture method (control)	Q ₁ X ₂ Q ₂		

Where,

- Q₁ = Pretest for the two groups before treatment,
X₁ = Teaching Method
X₂ = Traditional method
Q₂ = Posttest for the two groups after treatment.

Ninety-two (92) financial accounting students served as the population of the study. These students are presently in vocational II taking financial accounting as a subject in business department in the nine technical colleges located in Delta State. 54 financial accounting students in vocational II made up the sample for the study. The study employed purposive sampling technique in selecting students from five technical colleges of the nine technical colleges located in Delta State. Financial accounting achievement test (FAAT), was the instrument that was employed for the data collection which comprised questions derived from Vocational II scheme of work on financial accounting subject. Fifty (50) standardized NABTEB past questions between 2012 and 2022 multiple-choice test items with options A to D made up the instrument. Account topics covered in the test include: depreciation, manufacturing, non-profit making organizations account, single entry/ incomplete records and partnership account.

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The financial accounting achievement test (FAAT) instrument was validated by three specialists in Business Education from University of Benin, Benin City, one experienced financial accounting teacher in Issele-Uku Technical College in Delta State and one measurement and Evaluation specialist from the University of Benin.

Kuder-Richardson 21 formula approach was used to carry out the reliability of the study. This method was used because it is most suitable for multiple-choice test items. A pilot study was carried out with 20 financial accounting students in Oshimili North Local Government Area of Delta State who were part of the study geographical location; the scores obtained from the test, were subjected to the Kuder-Richardson 21 formula. A reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was derived. This authenticated that the instrument is suitable for this study.

Treatment Procedure

The teachers taking financial accounting in the school were subjected to training for a period of two weeks before the treatment exercise started. This was to prepare them ahead of time to know how to implement problem-based method of teaching during the period of the experimental exercise. The instrument (FAAT) was administered at the beginning of the experiment, to both treatment and control groups which served as a pre-test. This exercise was carried out by the trained financial accounting teachers. When the test was over, both the question papers and answer scripts were taken from the students. It was the same instrument that administered to the students after the experimental period, which lasted for six (6) weeks. The scores obtained from this, served as the post-test. The experimental procedure was implemented thus: two instructional packages were designed by the researcher. The first package hinged on instructional problem-based method while the second package was designed on the conventional teaching method. The questions covered were obtained from the same scheme of work. At the initial stage of the experiment, the students in both group (treatment and control) were served the pre-test. Immediately after this exercise, the regular financial accounting teachers initiated the experiment exercise in the technical colleges used and located in Delta State. The treatment groups were taught employing the instructional package for the experimental group while the control groups were taught with the instructional package meant for the control group. This experiment exercise lasted for a period of six (6) weeks and it was carried out during the usual school periods, according to the school time table in order not disrupt classes. The two groups at the end of the experiment were administered post-test.

The scores obtained were subjected to statistical analysis using the mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the analysis of co-variance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. When the p-value obtained was less than or equal to .05, the null hypothesis was not accepted but when the p-value obtained was greater than .05, the null hypothesis was accepted.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What is the academic performance of students taught using conventional methods and student taught employing problem-based instructional strategy?

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation of the Mean Academic Performance of Students taught using Conventional Methods and Students taught employing Problem Based Instructional Strategy

Strategies	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
		Mean (x)	SD	Mean (x)	SD	
Problem-based Teaching	36	5.86	1.72	16.16	1.89	10.30
Conventional (Control)	28	4.92	1.31	14.10	2.41	9.18

Results in table 1 reveals that students taught financial accounting adopting Problem-based instructional method obtained a mean score of 5.86 with a standard deviation of 1.72 in the pretest while a mean score of 16.16 with a standard deviation of 1.89 in the posttest making a pretest-post-test mean gain of 10.30. The Table also shows that students exposed to the Traditional teaching strategy had a mean score of 4.92 and a standard deviation of 1.31 in the pretest, a mean score of 14.10 and a standard deviation of 2.41 at posttest, making a mean gain of 9.18. This result indicates that the students acquired higher academic performance in posttest than in pretest.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students taught using conventional methods and students taught using problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting.

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Table 2: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Academic Performance Taught Financial Accounting

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	813.478 ^a	3	271.159	87.581	.000	.480	
Intercept	2255.435	1	2255.435	728.475	.000	.719	
Pretest (Covariate)	507.942	1	507.942	164.058	.000	.365	
Performance	297.185	2	148.593	47.993	.000	.252	
Error	882.390	65	3.096				
Total	70803.000	67					
Corrected Total	1695.869	67					

a. R Squared = .480 (Adjusted R Squared = .474)

Data in table 2 reveals that the ANCOVA analysis of academic performance of students taught financial accounting employing Problem solving instructional strategy as well as conventional instructional strategies in technical colleges located in Delta State. The result indicated that $F_{(2, 285)} = 47.993$, $p = .000$ significant at 0.05 alpha level. The results also indicated that treatment accounted for 25.2% of the variance in the dependent variable. This means that there is a notable or significant difference in the academic performance of students exposed to financial accounting employing Problem-based instructional strategy and conventional instructional strategies in technical colleges located in Delta State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected or not accepted. Thus, there is significant or notable difference between the academic performance of students taught with the conventional methods and students taught with problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting in favours of Problem-based teaching group.

Research Question Two

What is the academic performance of students taught using problem-based instructional strategy in financial accounting based on gender?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Academic Performance of Students Exposed to Problem Based Instructional Strategy in Financial Accounting

Groups	Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
			Mean (\bar{x})	SD	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	
Problem-based Teaching	Male	54	5.72	1.70	15.78	1.91	10.06
	Female	37	6.05	1.74	16.73	1.73	10.68
Traditnal (Control)	Male	56	4.86	1.37	13.77	2.49	8.91
	Female	49	5.00	1.26	14.49	2.83	9.49

Results in table 3 indicates the mean and standard deviation of academic performance of students exposed to financial accounting employing Problem-based Teaching Strategy and conventional instructional strategies by gender in technical colleges in Delta State. Results indicate that at pre-test, the males in the Problem-based Teaching Strategy obtained a mean score of 5.72 and a standard deviation of 1.70 whereas, at the posttest, the males obtained a mean score of 15.78, a standard deviation of 1.91 with a mean gain of 10.06. The females in the group had a mean score of 6.05 and a standard deviation of 1.74 at pretest, a mean score of 16.73 and a standard deviation of 1.73 at posttest and a mean gain of 10.68. For the Control group, males had a mean score of 4.86, a standard deviation of 1.37 in the pretest and a mean score of 13.77 and a standard deviation of 2.49 in the posttest resulting in a mean gain of 8.91. The females had a pretest mean score of 5.00, a standard deviation of 1.26, aposttest mean score of 14.49, a standard deviation of 2.83 and a mean gain of 9.49.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students taught using problem-based instructional strategy based on gender.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Academic Performance of Students Taught Financial Accounting Employing Problem-based Instructions by Gender

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	892.927 ^a	6	148.821	52.267	.000	.527	

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Intercept	2331.565	1	2331.565	818.866	.000	.744
Pretest (Covariate)	439.578	1	439.578	154.384	.000	.354
Gender	376.634	5	75.327	26.455	.000	.319
Error	802.941	282	2.847			
Total	70803.000	289				
Corrected Total	1695.869	288				

a. R Squared = .527 (Adjusted R Squared = .516)

Analysis in table 4 reveals the ANCOVA of academic performance of students exposed to financial accounting utilizing Problem-based instructional Strategy in technical colleges located in Delta State. The result indicated that $F_{(5, 282)} = 26.455$, $p = .000$ significant at 0.05 alpha level. Results also showed that treatment accounted for 31.9% of the variance in the dependent variable. It means that a notable difference exists in the achievement of students exposed to financial accounting employing problem-based instructional strategy in technical colleges in Delta State. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected not accepted. Hence, There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students taught using problem-based instructional strategy based on gender; where female students showed higher academic performance than their male counterparts in Problem-based teaching group.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the study indicates that students who were exposed to financial accounting utilizing problem-based instructional strategy performed better in post-test scores compared to students exposed to financial accounting employing the conventional method. This finding is in line with that of Olaoye and Adu (2015) who reported that Problem based learning had significant effect on achievement scores of students. The difference in the scores is due to exposing students to practical teaching and learning that resulted in the build capacity in solving complex questions. Also, the study showed that the female students outperformed the male students in financial accounting employing the problem-based instructional strategy. This finding corroborates the findings of Akpobroka (2024) who observed that female students exposed to problem-based learning did better than their male counterpart in achievement test.

CONCLUSION

With special reference to the research findings, conclusion can be made on the effect of problem-based instructional strategy on the academic performance of financial accounting students in technical colleges located in Delta State. Based on the data obtained from the test scores in course of this study, it has shown that the teaching of accounting subject depends largely on the blend of effective teaching aids, and the use of effective instructional method. The researcher therefore, inferred that problem-based instructional strategy possesses the capacity to enhancing the students' academic achievement in financial accounting in schools and colleges in Delta State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations were put forward based on the research findings:

1. Lessons on financial accounting should be taught utilizing problem-based instructional strategy regardless of the gender of students.
2. Problem-based instructional strategy should be employed by curriculum planners as an effective instructional method of financial accounting.
3. There should be regular workshops, seminars and symposiums by the Ministry of Technical Education and Post Primary Education Board for financial accounting teachers emphasizing the need of employing problem-based instructional strategy in the teaching and learning financial accounting.

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